

ESTIMATION OF COPPER AND NICKEL BY $\alpha\beta$ -DIOXIMINOACETOACET-*o*-CHLORANILIDE

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$\alpha\beta$ -Dioximinoacetoacet-*o*-chloranilide precipitates quantitatively copper as $CuC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$ at pH 7.1 to 8.9 and nickel as $NiC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$ at pH 4.4 to 9.4. Effect of some of the ions on the estimations of copper and nickel also has been investigated.

In continuation of our previous communications [this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 302, 735, 838], we present herein the results of our investigations on the gravimetric estimation of copper and nickel by $\alpha\beta$ -dioximinoacetoacet-*o*-chloranilide. With this reagent, copper forms a brown complex and nickel forms a yellow one, which are formulated as $MC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$ (where M=Cu or Ni). Copper and nickel can be quantitatively precipitated by this reagent under different conditions in presence of different ions under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

1% Alcoholic solution of $\alpha\beta$ -dioximinoacetoacet-*o*-chloranilide, prepared from acetoacet-*o*-chloranilide (Dave and Talati, *Curr. Sci.*, 1957, **26**, 326), was used in all the estimations. Solutions of copper chloride and nickel chloride and other reagents used were the same as mentioned previously.

Composition of the Complexes

The copper and nickel complexes were prepared and their compositions were determined as discussed earlier (*loc. cit.*).

(a) (Found: Cu, 11.11, 11.06. Calc. for $CuC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$: Cu, 11.09%).

(b) (Found: Ni, 10.35, 10.28. Calc. for $NiC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$: Ni, 10.33%).

The results suggest that the composition of the complexes can be represented as

where M = Cu or Ni.

Analytical procedure was the same as described previously (*loc. cit.*). The precipitates were weighed as $CuC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$ or $NiC_{20}H_{18}O_8N_6Cl_2$, the factors for copper and nickel being 0.1109 and 0.1033 respectively. Some of the results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

M taken.	M complex found.	M found.	Error.
Copper.			
7.85 mg.	70.6 mg.	7.83 mg.	-0.02 mg.
15.25	136.8	15.17	-0.08
30.50	275.0	30.50	± 0.00
Nickel.			
6.81	66.2	6.84	+0.03
13.22	128.4	13.26	+0.04

Effect of pH.—In order to study the pH range over which copper or nickel can be completely precipitated by this reagent, estimations of copper and nickel were carried out in solutions having different pH values. pH values of the undiluted filtrates were determined by L and N pH meter. The results, recorded in Table II, show that copper is completely precipitated by this reagent within the pH range 2.1 to 8.9 and nickel, in the pH range 4.4 to 9.4.

TABLE II

Cu taken.	pH.	Cu found.	Ni taken.	pH.	Ni found.
7.85 mg.	1.72	6.59 mg.	13.22 mg.	4.14	12.57 mg.
7.85	2.12	7.83	13.22	4.40	13.23
15.25	3.88	15.19	13.22	9.44	13.26
15.25	4.80	15.17			
7.85	8.92	7.81			

Effect of Anions and Cations.—Copper and nickel were estimated in presence of different ions by this reagent at pH 6 to 7. Some of the results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

M taken.	Salt added.	M found.	Error.
Copper.			
7.85 mg.	KBr, 2.0 g.	7.80 mg.	-0.05 mg.
7.85	K ₂ SO ₄ , 2.0	7.80	-0.05
7.85	BaCl ₂ , 0.75	7.81	-0.04
7.85	MgCl ₂ , 0.50	7.76	-0.09
Nickel.			
6.81	NaAc, 2.0	6.82 mg.	+0.01 mg.
6.81	NaNO ₃ , 2.0	6.84	+0.03
6.81	KI, 2.0	6.86	+0.05
6.81	K ₂ SO ₄ , 2.0	6.88	+0.07
6.81	CaCl ₂ , 0.55	6.80	-0.01
6.81	BaCl ₂ , 0.75	6.77	-0.04
6.81	Sr(NO ₃) ₂ , 0.65	6.76	-0.05
6.81	MgCl ₂ , 0.50	6.77	-0.04
6.81	ZnSO ₄ , 0.036	6.85	+0.04
6.81	CdSO ₄ , 0.032	6.82	+0.01
6.81	HgCl ₂ , 0.034	6.87	+0.06

The results show that the ions under study cause little or no interference to the estimations.

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